

Role of Education on Voting Behavior in Afghanistan

Mr. Gulab Mir Rahmany

PhD. Research Scholar, Department of Sociology
University College for Arts and Social Sciences (UCA&SS)
Osmania University, Hyderabad, Telangana State

ABSTRACT

The role of Education is very important on voting behavior in the election process, because education is a ring connected families with the country's political system, according to the constitution and the treaty stipulates that Afghanistan is committed to implementing them, Despite all problems the significant gains achieved is there than in the past, today, education is one of the fundamental process for strengthening democracy and social awareness among the citizens entire the society.

According to Article 43 the constitution of Afghanistan, education is the right all citizens of the country and has a bachelor's degree in public educational institutions are provided for free by the government constitution 2003. For this purpose the government is obliged to balanced expansion of education all over Afghanistan, providing compulsory secondary education, design and implement effective programs, This article of the constitution to the need for access to quality and equitable education for all citizens, regardless of affiliation, cultural, linguistic, ethnic, gender and physical status and their physical states, On the other hand, Article 44 of the constitution of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, especially guarantee, education for women. Base on this principle. The government is obliged to take effective programs for balancing and promoting women's education plan and implement to women's participation in the voting process have an active share. Afghanistan's education institutions have long existed in the past decade with the help of the international community and political stability has been impressive, But generally balanced growth that was expected has been not done, in terms of quantitative changed but in terms of quality is not satisfactory change in the country.

KEYWORDS: Education, voting behavior, challenges, Afghanistan

INTRODUCTION

Education affairs leading cause of institutionalization of democracy changed to a democratic system in Afghanistan. Higher education is essential for the people of Afghanistan because Afghanistan is struggling in the trap of tribal values and traditions, the values and traditions led to bloody wars between different ethnic groups in the country, Educational institutions if the country develops and grows causes the new values in society. One of the important elements of democracy for the people is spreads the values of democracy and the new values instead of the values and traditions of tribal life of Afghans means the catalog. The new values will undoubtedly strengthen democracy and democratic values will be as well. Impossible without educated understanding of democratic values and democratic values in a society without a doubt that the vast majority of illiterate people are not sustainable. As mentioned above, institutions of education has a significant role in the process of social institutions of and democracy in the country.

Therefore, the government can be incorporated into lesson plans and content children about the state of mind, peace, democracy, voting, and develop and shape. If the government to consolidate democracy strengthens the foundations of public governance, peace, achieve the strategic development thinking, a long-term program knows it must act through the institutions of the State. Moreover the serious attention to educational institutions, programs and curriculum content is under consideration. Because education is the only tool that can save us from democracy blind and seer.

After the fall of the Taliban regime the new government under the name of democracy, elections implemented with big issues, the process of voting in Afghanistan face big challenge to make the people unsatisfactory. the main issues on the way of democracy in the during 14 years were the issues of ethnic, sectarian, linguistic, lack of awareness of the

electoral process, interventions external and internal entire the country.

Even election is one the word Bailment from the perspective of Holly book Quran and mention in the verse Nesa (58):

إِنَّ اللَّهَ يَأْمُرُكُمْ أَنْ تُؤَدُّوا الْأَمَانَاتِ إِلَىٰ أَهْلِهَا وَإِذَا حَكَمْتُمْ بَيْنَ النَّاسِ أَنْ تَحْكُمُوا بِالْعَدْلِ إِنَّ اللَّهَ نِعِمَّا يَعِظُكُمْ بِهِ إِنَّ اللَّهَ كَانَ سَمِيعًا بَصِيرًا

Meaning:

Allah commands you that deposits to their owners and when you judge between people to judge with justice really good at what God admonishes you to that hearing, the seeing of God (58) (Afghanistan's Independent Election Commission broadcasting public awareness(2013,pp,21-12).

This research shows only families with the knowledge and literate enough, especially mothers, the importance of education for children, especially for girls understand the context of their participation in education and facilitate their awareness Section contribution to the democratic process been outstanding. However, due to limitations in the years ahead, the lack of capacity to budget and implement programs for the development of education Ministry of Education has failed to awareness of citizens portions of democracy highlight one of the major problems system of democratic consciousness of citizens, for improving the awareness among of the people.

Review of Literature:

Knowledge the most basic foundations of a progressive society and modern form and this one a case Pause human society in the past century and now is, society, primitive, based on preconditions and many restrictions faced by society ago of modernity anyone had the right to education, knowledge and learning for minority community, including businessmen, officials, local authorities and landowners were considered, it was possible.

But the majority were serving the capitalist and was working as a slave, in this era of knowledge was at a low level, so that schools and religious centers of

mathematics, geometry, astronomy was taught, But by stepping society in an era of ultra-primitive and advanced, knowledge of particular interest were developed, today we are witnessing in the 21st century competition based on knowledge progresses result of science in the hands of anyone can observed. Cell phones, computers, televisions are all examples of modern science is at home with each of us and the countries of the first world in this century a special focus on technology and science and to seek to challenge the political, military, economic are all based on science The ground material can satisfy human needs in the next few years will be oil, gas, Polycarbonate, coal and so on. Examples that can be cited for the decline in the near future, humanity will need, However, other materials can be found and that the human endeavor to meet the needs of technology and other resources, is today's war and interventions major countries in the world focused on this principle, and for access to ingredients listed several measures have interests of their own their supplies, Today, knowledge is developed beyond what we think, But Afghanistan's role in the country's zero in three decades of war in Afghanistan has brought improvements to the survivors and the homeless. In three decades, the fatal blow to the body of scientific knowledge and fostering stricken country these look no progress had, in developed countries usually Statistics literate than 90 percent of Now, Afghanistan Statistics Thirty-three percent of the show, But today it is happiness time during 13 years, Afghanistan has made remarkable progress in education sector, And each year thousands of students from universities and graduate schools are thousands of other schools, study clarify so at the beginning of the most basic foundations of a country's progress Hatch modern high number of countries in science and basic practical knowledge prior, The sector is still failing

Afghanistan war still existed 30 years and this period will not be compensated. Today hopefully, education in the country young people in different places and in the most difficult situations with enthusiasm and interest in working with their specific knowledge of the business.

Given all expectations with leaders of the national unity government is using the opportunity provided, Try to help the international community and donor countries to Afghanistan draw. And education for young people so provide in the future of our country with the crisis of illiteracy and low literacy forever dead and need to hire a cadre of specialists from foreign countries and the brain drain by itself from other lands not.(Mehdi, Parsa (2014, 12,28).

To quoted "Dr.Qaradawi go to the elections and expressed in terms of voting rights for the good of fact, the testimony of faithfulness career. God has ordered to vote is certainly an understatement Read the testimony of a great sin" vote is very important because if vote is

Definition of Education

Education is the technical way of teaching and correcting relies on scientific methods and is based self understanding of , Every teacher needs to learn to establish your career and why one of the major fields of study at colleges and universities in the world(Dehkhoda dictionary)

Education is the social engineering of human beings" Emile Durkheim said"

Why Education is important?

Producer Gay and fitness education led to humans. The inability of humans at birth everyone is clear what factors than education makes man powerless as individuals mature and capable of traits of human such as dignity, honor, respect, sportsmanship, generosity courage, altruism , wisdom, and justice be done. Education and training in human society is healthy only human beings possess the characteristics listed above returns, If people are not educated or trained not to affect human society. Not only these characteristics do not appear in his actions like other animals, he will remain as primitive and instinctive. Therefore uneducated person will be the big risk entire the society. In another word voter education ensure that voters are ready and willing to participate

in voting process and selecting appropriate government which is effective and suitable to individual entire the society.(Sardar,Mohammad,Saii (2008,octovber,15,10:32).

Is Voter Education Sufficient for Democracy?

Voter education is more important and make ensure the voters to effectively exercise their voting right to express their political willing through election process, and take prepare to motivate in participation of voting process if the voters do not educate and not prepare they will not be motivate to take part in voting trend.(ACE Electoral Knowledge Network (1998A).

Definition of Voting Behavior

Voting behavior is the individual expressing and preference in to collective choice for selecting their candidate or political party in election process.(Dictionary of sociology,original,1998).

What is Voting Behavior?

Voting behavior is the way which individual, willing to vote for their choice representative, in democratic society and arrive on their political leader they decision .in another word Voting behavior is the decision and form of political willing which is voter take decision to use their freedom practice on democratic arena.(Oriavwote, 2000).

Methodology

In this study descriptive research along with secondary and primary data by questioner's tools of collected data has been used.

Objective:

1. To know about the value of education development on voting process
2. To know about voting awareness and Impact of education on voting behaviour

Hypothesis of this study:

1. quality of education compare to the quantity is very low entire the country
2. Lack of political awareness is the big issue among the people during voting behaviour

The current situation of education in Afghanistan:

Afghanistan, including post-conflict countries considered that in the last three decades hurt more in the field of education has seen. after the fall of the Taliban regime gates of schools on the face of all citizens Afghan girls and boys reopened opportunities conducive learning was so young people can take advantage of education is the right of access to the statistics report of the study has found from the ministry of education access.

In 2003 less than one million boys, had access to education, according to statistics of the Ministry of Education (2012) 9. 5 million students are general education schools. However, due to the problems and challenges facing education for girls only about 39 percent (3,549,000) of general education students are girls. Given that the number of girls and mandatory eligible school in the country is about 6 million people, 39 percent index (3,549,000) represents the distance is access to education for boys and girls, According to the figures and the above criteria, about 41 percent of girls, about 2. 5 million girls have access to education.

In addition, the number of female graduates from the public education system is about 64 000,

people, about 34 percent of total public education graduates, class 12 form. The low number of female students in schools, mean little girls access to education and training programs is teacher training. In addition the existence of a small number of students and graduates of general education girl means reducing their role in national development programs and their social role.(Annual progress report on Education,2012).

Civil Society: is an important element of the democratic system in a country with no civil society, without basic social concept of contemporary democratic system will be totalitarian content. Meanwhile, civil society must be enlightened by measures, in coordination with the Electoral Commission, and conducting workshop, improve the awareness of equal right between male and female, removing discrimination entire the society and order to raise awareness, attract the citizens specially women and the light of values of a democratic system because till now more numbers of women are not participating in voting process in the rural areas. Therefore with increasing education can improving dimension awareness and provide chance to everyone use their own civil rights as it is.(Abdulkabir,Ranjbar,2014,p,6)

Primary Data:**Table 1.1 Level of Education and Occupation in Afghanistan**

Education Status in Afghanistan			Occupational Status in Afghanistan		
Education Status in	Frequency	Percent	Occupational Status	Frequency	Percent
Primary	1	0.7	Labour	6	4
Secondary	18	12	Agriculture	8	5.3
BA	122	81.3	Business	2	1.3
PG Diploma	4	2.7	Gov service	51	34
Master Degree	3	2	Private sector	28	18.7
PhD	1	0.7	Other	55	36.7
Others	1	0.7	Total	150	100
Total	150	100			

In this part of primary data show (81.13%) of the respondent were BA and more number of the Respondent were working in government service.

Table 1.2 Level of voting awareness in Afghanistan

Do you know anything about voting process in Afghanistan?		
knowing of voting system	Frequency	Percent
Yes	129	86
No	21	14
Total	150	100

In this research study shows out of 100% 14% of the educated people don't know anything about voting process, out of 150 responding only 129; responder knows what vote is about.

Table 1.3 Tools of Public awareness in the society

Which of the following information is important for voting awareness in Afghanistan?		
Tools of Public awareness	Frequency	Percent
TV	14	9.3
News paper	1	0.7
Public awareness	10	6.7
internet	4	2.7
Friends and community	2	1.3
All above	112	74.7
any other	7	4.7
Total	150	100

In this tabulation shows more (6.7) people believe public awareness is most important for public awareness of election process and out of 100% (74%) people believe all social networks is useful for having information about voting process.

MAJOR CHALLENGES OVER THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN AFGHANISTAN

However, efforts have been made but problems and challenges in the field of education in Afghanistan over to Afghan education system and strengthening the educational institutions that can be mentioned...

1. **Security:** Security is one of the preconditions of basic education for girls. No security, many families are not willing to send their daughters to school. The safety of girls in education, social security. Many schools lack the necessary facilities for the enrollment of girls. Mansion and the lack of protection and distance of schools from

homes, especially girls in rural areas is one of the major problems and challenges. Therefore a large number of families are not willing to send their daughters to school without the protective walls of the building.

2. **The weakness of the rule of law:** the rule of law in the country is extremely weak. Many of the powerful and those who defy the law are always fled from the law. Such a situation the security challenges facing girls and their families with a non-solution to the problem that access to education for girls has become a major challenge.
3. **Geographical situation and distance of schools:** On the one hand transport facilities in rural areas of the country and the distance between home and school girls is faced with many dangers, weak security presence in schools are more difficult.
4. **Financial position:** Afghanistan is a poor country about 36 percent of the population unable to meet their basic needs are basic, The per capita income in the country is estimated to be around 640 US dollars annual
5. **High growth of population:** population growth causes poverty, unemployment families, families that their children do not have the ability to fund education for the sake having a lot of children, including girls deprived of access to education.
6. **Traditional Culture Society:** On the other hand, since Afghanistan is a largely traditional, many families prefer to invest more in their sons. The same problem is to reduce the access of girls to education.
7. **Cultural situation:** in Afghanistan is a country of traditional and restrictive cultural function, Cultural norms of the country, especially for girls and women have imposed many limitations. for instance they believe females should be in chart of house only
8. **Lack of female teachers:** In addition to the above factors, lack of a large number of districts of the country and even in the absence of female teachers is one of the main reasons is the lack of participation of girls in education. Non-participation of girls in education, especially in

secondary schools will greatly reduce the number of Grade 12 girls. As a result, girls' access to teachers decreases.

social traditions their daughters to schools that male teachers have been hired, do not send”

9. **Taliban threats:** The school fire risk other processes of education in Afghanistan, the enemies of science and culture in the past few years hundreds of schools burned down and hundreds of teachers and students killed and thousands of children Under intimidation have had to leave school.(Aqila,Rashidi,2013,11, 17, Daily 8 am).

"Siddiq Patman, deputy minister of Education, Education Afghanistan exclusive interview with BBC said that in the areas of female teachers in schools are not present and the public because of

CHALLENGE ON EDUCATION AND VOTING PROCESS IN AFGHANISTAN

The constitution of Afghanistan has provision to all individual that who are eighteen years or more than that is eligible or can get the benefit of the vote. Afghanistan is the country which has the high rate of illiterate, ethic issues and with having different challenges mention in the below table:

Table 1.4 Challenge impact on Education and voting behaviour in Afghanistan

S/n	Type of Challenges	S/n	Type of Challenges
1	Ethnics	13	Foreign intervention
2	Language issues	14	Purchasing voter cards
3	Warlord force /gun holder	15	Ballot stuffing
4	Corruption	16	Religion issues
5	Taliban threaten	17	Election Campaign
6	Lack of security	18	Mass illiteracy
7	Fraud voter card	19	Discrimination
8	Voting instead of women	20	Issue Voting
9	voting one man more than one time	21	Social class
10	Lack rule of law	22	Locality
11	obtaining vote card under age	23	Lack of women image in the voter cards
12	Dumpling voter cards	24	Age and background

The three decade civil war and high rate of illiteracy put its impact on the view of the view and opinion of the common people today most of the people believe on the manifestos which is declaring by candidate during campaign unfortunately after the wining of the particular candidate the manifest will be remain in the text noting will practice at all. (Babak,Dehmanesh,2009,10,21).

According different reports and journal There are more other the factors which are influencing on individual voting behavior in the country like interfering of foreigner countries, political leaders,

dependency and weathers are considerable .(Taher Qaderi 2014,april,04,Friday).

SOLUTION AND SUGGESTION

In order to reduce the problems and find solutions to the problems of boys and girls access to education and long-awareness of citizens regarding the competence of individual voting and elections and acceptable for all design and commissioning of a resolution to be considered.

1. Hire more female teachers and administrative staff, especially in rural areas;
2. The allocation of salary incentives and land-living female teachers from urban schools to rural schools will be moved; and equip girls to surrounding schools, water facilities and toilets.
3. Establish local schools and extension offices in remote areas and distributing food and stationery for poor students;
4. Strengthening school assembly; and increasing the share of people in the construction of school buildings
5. More focus on training female teachers in primary teacher training in teacher training programs.
6. See accelerated training for teachers with less than grade 12 education; 8 non-centralized education administration, particularly in the area of planning.
7. Increase the election public awareness among the people and preachers attentions
8. Election is not based on the principles of personal interests, regional or ethnic.
9. This is so that people will be trained to enforce a reform program through which to understand what kind of person is appropriate, And what characteristics they should be moral and intellectual talent.
10. Voter's Education Awareness Programs should be conducted on a regular basis in the senior secondary schools, colleges and other Educational Institutions. Electoral process and awareness should be included as a part of the curriculum
11. To ensure that people understand their right as voters and exercise that right with full knowledge and responsibility

For the development of a quality of education and developing transparency voting processes ,education and public awareness should be increase among youth and common citizen of the

county they need more attention of the government scheme and policy.

References

1. Annual progress report on Education (1391), the Ministry of Education, Kabul, Afghanistan
2. Aqila,Rashidi,(2013,November 17, Daily 8 am newspaper, Kabul University Afghanistan
3. ACE Electoral Knowledge Network (1998A) ACE Encyclopaedia First Published Network.
4. Abdulkabir,Ranjbar (2014,p,6) Election from the perspective of Afghanistan, Civil society Kabul, Afghanistan
5. Babak,Dehmanesh,(2009,10,21),Kabul University, Afghanistan
6. Dictionary of sociology, original(1998,Published by oxford University
7. Dehkhoda dictionary.
8. IEC head of public awareness(2013,p,12)Collection of articles, Kabul Afghanistan
9. Mehdi, Parsa (2014, 12,28) National Coalition of Afghanistan Kabul, Afghanistan
10. Oriavwote, (2000) Sk.Balogunadd and P.O.olapegba.
11. Sardar, Mohammad, Saii (2008, octovber, 15,10:32,Kabul,University, Afghanistan.
12. Taher Qaderi (2014, April, 04, Friday.